

Chronic wetland degradation due to excessive urbanization and its impact on biodiversity in Maharashtra, India

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ABSTRACT

Wetlands are the kidneys of the earth. They protect from different natural calamities at different times. They are the source of food and resting space for human, birds, and animals. But over the period, wetlands are degrading, and the area of wetlands is declining fast due to manmade factors. Urbanisation is increasing fast in India. The Maharashtra state is not an exception to the growth of urbanisation. But due to changes in the land use pattern in Maharashtra state, the wetlands are degraded and declining fast. Wetlands are affected most in the Kokan region of Maharashtra due to excessive migration and urbanisation. The built-up area is increasing, and crop land is decreasing in Western Maharashtra. The following land is increasing in Aurangabad. The evergreen forest cover is decreasing in Kokan, Amravati region. The island's wetlands are declining fast in the Kokan region. New infrastructure projects and urbanisation are responsible for declining in island wetlands. Water bodies related land cover has increased in Amravati and in the Nasik region. The number of lakes is more in Western Maharashtra. The creeks and beaches, mangroves, saltpans aqua culture is more prevalent in the Kokan region, but it is vanishing fast. The ordinary least squares regression results show that total land is negatively correlated to salt-affected land, wetlands. Therefore, all the wetland in the state needs to be protected, and people must be made aware about its uses and future negative effects. The state government must publish a report on the sustainability of wetlands in urban areas. Such policies will protect wetlands and provide a habitat for life. Environmental sustainability will be achieved in a highly urbanised state in India.

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Introduction

Wetlands play a crucial role in natural habitats and in protecting from natural disasters. They provide globally significant social, economic, and environmental benefits. Important wetland functions include water storage, groundwater recharge, storm protection, flood mitigation, shoreline stabilization, erosion control, retention of carbon, nutrients, sediments, and pollutants. Wetlands also produce goods that have a significant economic value, such as clean water, fisheries, timber, peat, wildlife resources, and tourism opportunities (Abera Hirpo, 2018). Instead of knowing all the benefits, the wetlands are destroyed due to excessive urbanisation, conversion of land, and lack of care. The serious concerns voiced among scientists, planners, sociologists, politicians, and economists are to conserve and preserve the natural resources. Wetlands can directly change chemical and physical properties such as nutrient availability, soil salinity, sediment properties, etc. These modifications of the physiochemical environment, in turn, have a direct impact on the biotic response in the wetland. When hydrological conditions in wetlands change even very slightly, the biota may respond with massive changes in species composition, richness, and ecosystem productivity. Wetlands are formed by the interaction between terrestrial and aquatic systems and are of substantial importance in the study of global environmental change. However, the global wetland area is rapidly declining, and wetlands are experiencing environmental stress caused by human activities. Existing methods neither consider thought-out human pressure factors nor depict the spatial variation in wetland risks in detail (Huang et al., 2022). But wetlands are important for the ecosystem. Wetlands provide critical habitat for flora and fauna. Wetlands provide fundamental ecological services. They are the source of biodiversity at all levels of species, genetic, and ecosystem. Wetlands play a key role in climate change adaptation and mitigation. It is a great source of economic, scientific, cultural, and recreational value for the community. Wetlands support the livelihood of animals, including mammals, birds, fish, etc. Wetlands are the nurseries of many species. Many birds and animals live in wetlands and use them for reproduction. Wetlands recycle nutrients, which are critical in the overall functioning of biodiversity. In urban areas, wetlands provide a number of services such as cooling the urban environment, habitat for wildlife, and recreational opportunities. Water quality improvement to cope with the effects of climate change. In urban areas, population growth, construction, land conversion, and drainage lines affect wetlands. All factors create pressures on the wetland ecosystem in the state. Such pressure reduces the functionality of wetlands. It reduces the well-being of humans and animals through climate change. Land use get change from wetland to

non-wetland activities in cities. There is an encroachment on wetlands. The government plans roads, bridges, airports, metro stations, and recreational activities at wetland sites. Solid waste is disposed of in wetlands in the urban areas of Mumbai and the Thane district. All the above activities are responsible for flooding in urban areas and wetland destruction. Excessive fishing also effects on wetland system. The cultural and religious point of view, such as immersion of idol Ganesh and other religious offerings, such as Poojas, degrade wetlands. Thousands of people visit the wetlands to perform religious rituals. Such activities do not help wetlands to grow and flourish. At high urbanisation, such activities are responsible for wetland degradation and environmental pollution. In Mumbai and the Thane district, water pollution levels are increasing continuously. People throw solid waste and sewage water into the river and the sea. The stormwater and sewage water degrade the wetlands. Tourism activities affecting wetland sites. There are a few recreational activities at wetland sites. People visit such sites, eat food, pollute the environment, and destroy biodiversity. The commercial activities and tourist sites near wetland sites affect migratory and local birds and their habitats. The number of birds is already declining due to urban infrastructure. The biodiversity at Uran, Panvel, Mumbai suburbs, Ratnagiri, and Thane city declined due to continuous human economic activities near wetlands. Urban wetlands are more vulnerable to human intervention and destruction than any other ecosystem. (Alikhani et al., 2021). Due to the large scale of migration, the biodiversity in different developing regions in the state. Being that wetlands are part of environmentally provided assets that make up our natural capital, the depletion of a large portion of them indicates that the welfare of our environment is in a poor state. To sustain the ecosystem, environmental assets must be maintained, or at least not depleted (Amenu et al., 2017).

Data

We have collected the secondary data from the Ministry of Environment and Forests, Government of India. The region-specific indicators and geographically specific data are collected from the website of the Government of Maharashtra. The land use statistics of Maharashtra state give a bifurcation of land in 2005, 2011, and 2015. We classified and analysed the land use statistics to understand the reduction in wetlands by regions in the state. We have referred to newspapers such as The Times of India, Maharashtra Times, and Business Line to understand current issues of wetlands in the state. All the environmental reports of India and the state Government of Maharashtra have been referred. We analysed data in SPSS and R software used for regression analysis.

Economic model: 1000/500

We have developed an economic model to understand the types of wetlands and subcomponents of wetlands.

$$\sum_{n=1}^t LM = (TL/(A, B, Bu, Fo, Gg, WL))*100. \quad (1)$$

Where Lm means land in Maharashtra used for a specific purpose. It is further divided as land under the use of Agriculture, Barren/unculturable/ Wastelands, Built-up, Forest Grass / Grazing, Water lands/water bodies.

$$\sum_{n=1}^t A = f(CL, F, P) \quad (2)$$

Where land use for Agriculture in the state is divided as Crop land, fallow, and plantation.

$$\sum_{n=1}^t B = f(BR, GR, SAL, SA, SCL) \quad (3)$$

In the above equation, Barren/unculturable/ Wastelands is related to Barren Rocky, Gullied / Ravenous Land, Salt Affected Land, Sandy Area, and Scrub Land

$$\sum_{n=1}^t Bu = f(Mi, R, U) \quad (4)$$

Built-up land is divided into land under mining, rural, and urban areas.

$$\sum_{n=1}^t Fo = f(De, Evg, FP, SF, SM) \quad (5)$$

The forest land is related to deciduous, evergreen/semi-evergreen, Forest Plantation, scrub Forest, and Swamp / Mangroves

$$\sum_{n=1}^t WI = f(IW, CW, Ri, WB) \quad (6)$$

Wetlands are divided into four categories: Inland Wetland, Coastal Wetland, River/Stream/Canals, and Water bodies

Inland wetland

Inland wetlands are of two categories. Firstly, it is located slightly away from the sea. The high tide water enters such inland wetlands. There could be another type of natural place with minimal human interference. There could be man-made inland wetlands also.

$$\sum_{n=1}^t IWn = f(L, OWL, HAW, RW, WL, RS)$$

(7)

Inland wetlands are further divided as Lakes/ponds, ox-bow lakes/cut-off meanders, riverine wetlands, and waterlogged rivers/streams.

$$\sum_{n=1}^t IWmm = f(RB, TP, WL, SP)$$

(8)

Inland wetlands-Manmade deals with reservoirs/Barrages, Tanks/ponds, waterlogged

Coastal wetlands

Coastal wetlands are in the Konkan region of Maharashtra, and they are of the following types.

$$\sum_{n=1}^t CWn = f(C, SB, IMF, SM, M)$$

(9)

Coastal wetlands are divided into creeks, sand/beach, intertidal mud flats, salt marshes, and mangroves.

$$\sum_{n=1}^t Cmm = f(SP, AP)$$

(10)

Coastal wetlands-manmade is divided into salt pans and aquaculture ponds

Maharashtra

Maharashtra is the second-largest state in the country, occupying nearly 10 percent of the total geographical area. The state has 307748km geographical area over 800 km, from east to west. Maharashtra state has 700 km from North to South coastline of 720 km along the west. The state is divided into two major physiographic division viz the Deccan plateau and the coastal region known as Kokan. Physical divisions of the state comprise the 3 parts based on its physical characteristics, viz., the Maharashtra plateau, the Sahyadri Range, and the Kokan coastal strip. The North plateau is flanked by the Satpuda ranges. It runs in the East and West directions in the state. The river Narmada flows along the northern boundary of Maharashtra and after major rivers like Krishna, Godavari, Bhima, Penganga, Wardha, and Tapi-Purna. The Western Ghats are known as the Sahyadri mountain ranges. It has a height of 1000- 1200 m above sea level. It runs parallel to the seacoast with many offshoots branching eastwards from the main ranges (Satmala, Ajanta, Harishchandra, Balaghat, and Mahadeo). The Western Ghats are known for their biodiversity in the country. The most special hills are Trambakeshwar, Matheran, and the Mahabaleshwar plateau. Kalsubai is the highest peak at an altitude of 1650m.

Most of the rivers originate from the Sahyadri and then divide to join the Eastward and Westward flowing rivers. There are a number of ghats, such as Thal, Bor, Kumbharli, Amba, Phonda, and Amboli. The narrow strip between the Sahayadri and the Arabian Sea is known as the Kokan Coastal strip. It is the only 50 km wide with a wider north and a narrower south strip. Important creeks in Kokan are Terekhol, Vijaydurg, Rajapuri, Raigad, Dabhol, Daramthar, Thane, and Vasai. Important rivers in Kokan are Ulhas, Savitri, Vashishthi, and Shastri. Maharashtra state has huge natural resources, but due to high urbanisation, there is continuous degradation of the environment. The state is divided into five administrative regions: Marathwada, Kokan, Vidharba, Western Maharashtra, and Aurangabad.

Figure 1. Regions in Maharashtra

Land use pattern in Maharashtra

We have analysed the secondary data from land use statistics for 2005, 2011 and 2015 year to observe the changes took place in land use pattern in Maharashtra. Maharashtra is highly urbanised state in India. Due to excessive migration, the agriculture and marshy land is getting converted into residential area. The inland wetlands are also dumped with solid waste and sewage water.

Table 1. The land use pattern in 2005, 2011 and 2015: Comparative analysis (Percent)

Type of land	Subtype	Kokan			western Maharashtra			Nasik			Amravati		
		2005	2011	2015	2005	2011	2015	2005	2011	2015	2005	2011	2015
Agriculture	Crop land	4.75	3.68	3.77	25.19	20.43	18.96	0.04	17.76	20.36	33.27	12.74	16.82
	Fallow	13.96	11.40	8.51	24.70	20.62	27.52	0.03	19.49	17.47	34.23	6.82	15.28
	Plantation	89.31	78.92	72.32	2.28	0.51	0.44	0.02	11.94	10.12	1.73	1.26	6.17
Barren/ unculturable/ Wastelands	Barren Rocky	27.29	14.90	12.08	63.81	38.93	30.27	0.11	33.84	34.24	6.55	0.97	2.47
	Gullied / Ravinous Land	0.00	0.27	0.40	3.55	5.83	2.14	0.28	56.61	53.13	2.60	3.30	36.45
	Salt Affected Land	15.59	65.71	76.42	84.41	34.29	23.58	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	Sandy Area	82.95	90.83	76.55	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	3.32	17.05	0.00	16.86
	Scrub Land	24.91	22.66	21.92	34.97	25.87	32.18	0.04	14.13	15.29	21.68	6.28	7.23
Built-up	Mining	19.86	20.63	20.50	12.28	9.45	12.62	0.02	6.88	7.94	12.63	28.48	16.47
	Rural	17.36	16.67	16.65	23.05	20.02	20.66	0.03	15.56	16.71	24.82	15.80	11.71
	Urban	28.72	22.52	23.08	26.31	17.25	26.97	0.03	8.66	14.75	15.28	14.97	7.18
Forest	Deciduous	9.49	10.09	10.06	7.12	8.54	4.37	0.03	9.02	13.44	5.30	48.84	16.45
	Evergreen/Semi evergreen	59.95	55.80	54.48	40.04	31.84	44.79	0.00	0.43	0.72	0.00	0.00	0.00
	Forest Plantation	0.31	0.27	0.26	3.15	1.18	1.84	0.00	1.41	1.03	0.06	95.60	0.92
	Scrub Forest	12.71	7.51	8.64	16.66	15.72	10.80	0.09	29.46	39.97	16.88	11.61	18.70
	Swamp Mangroves /	100.00	100.00	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Grass / Grazing	Grass / Grazing	4.00	0.00	0.00	8.57	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Wetlands / Water bodies	Inland Wetland	100.00	28.11	11.61	0.00	16.27	0.00	0.00	0.44	6.91	0.00	43.20	4.95

	Coastal Wetland	92.47	99.88	99.87	7.53	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.07	0.07	0.00	0.00	0.06
	River/Stream/Canals	14.79	11.20	11.19	19.75	15.58	16.02	0.05	17.75	20.31	22.19	24.38	10.18
	Water bodies	5.22	4.26	4.69	30.55	19.60	22.83	0.04	15.74	16.90	30.22	17.58	12.62

Source: Ministry of Environment and Forests, GoI

Table 1 (continued)

		Nagpur			Aurangabad		
		2005	2011	2015	2005	2011	2015
Agriculture	Crop land	21.05	28.22	12.36	15.70	17.17	27.73
	Fallow	17.55	30.96	8.90	9.53	10.72	22.32
Barren/ unculturable/ Wastelands	Plantation	5.41	2.40	8.71	1.24	5.34	2.24
	Barren Rocky	0.54	10.86	1.51	1.71	0.50	19.43
	Gullied / Ravinous Land	83.31	0.21	4.07	10.27	33.79	3.81
	Salt Affected Land	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	Sandy Area	0.00	0.00	1.58	0.00	9.17	1.69
Builtup	Scrub Land	9.51	24.24	7.41	8.89	6.81	15.96
	Mining	20.50	18.15	32.85	34.71	16.42	9.62
	Rural	15.17	20.23	15.91	19.56	11.72	18.35
Forest	Urban	9.76	29.66	15.92	19.89	6.94	12.09
	Deciduous	18.49	7.49	50.81	59.57	16.01	4.86
	Evergreen/Semi-evergreen	0.00	11.92	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	Forest Plantation	0.65	0.70	95.90	95.86	0.85	0.05
	Scrub Forest	32.90	14.37	11.99	20.77	21.33	9.89
Grass / Grazing	Swamp / Mangroves	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Wetlands / Water bodies	Grass / Grazing	0.00	0.00	0.00	87.43	0.00	0.00
	Inland Wetland	0.00	0.00	76.53	0.00	11.98	0.00
	Coastal Wetland	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.05	0.00

	River/Stream/Canals	12.30	20.83	24.39	30.92	10.27	17.91
	Water bodies	12.67	30.95	20.00	21.30	11.87	22.96

Source: Ministry of Environment and Forests, GoI

The land use pattern in Maharashtra is presented in Table 1. Crop land in Western Maharashtra has declined from 25.19% to 18.19% from 2005 to 2015. The following land has declined from 13.96 per cent to 8.51 per cent from 2005 to 2015 in Western Maharashtra. High urbanisation is responsible for the decline in crop land in the region. The government converts agricultural land to residential category land. The land has increased from 15.70 per cent to 22.73 per cent in Aurangabad from 2005 to 2015. Plantation related land declined from 89.31 per cent to 72.32 per cent from 2005 to 2015 in Kokan. The plantation has increased in Aurangabad from 9.53 per cent to 22.32 per cent from 2005 to 2015. Farmers are producing cash crops such as sugarcane and fruits in this region. In Western Maharashtra, plantation has declined from 02.28 per cent to 0.44 per cent from 2005 to 2015. But it has declined by a small percentage. The Burren Rockey has declined from 63.18 per cent to 30.27 per cent in Western Maharashtra. In Kokan, the salt-affected land has increased from 15.59 per cent to 76.42 per cent from 2005 to 2015. In Western Maharashtra, the salt-affected land also declined from 84.41 per cent to 23.58 per cent from 2005 to 2015. The land under scrub has declined in Kokan from 24.91 per cent to 21.92 per cent from 2005 to 2015. In the Kokan region, there is a minor decline of land use for built-up area, i.e., 17.36 per cent to 16.65 per cent in rural parts. People are migrating from rural to urban areas. People are not building houses in rural areas due to a lack of infrastructure facilities. The built-up area from the rural part in Aurangabad has declined from 34.71 per cent to 9.62 per cent from 2005 to 2015. In the Amravati region, the built-up area in rural areas has declined from 24.82 per cent to 11.71 per cent from 2005 to 2015. A livelihood is only possible with ownership of land. It is not possible to live in a rural area and cultivate infertile, unirrigated land. Most of the poor people leave rural areas and travel to urban areas for work. As far as deciduous forests are concerned, it is increasing in (0.03 per cent to 13.44 per cent) in the Nasik region from 2005 to 2015. The evergreen /semi-evergreen forest area is declining in the Kokan region (59.95 per cent to 54.48 per cent) from 2005 to 2015. The evergreen forest in the Aurangabad region has declined from 59.57 per cent to 4.86 per cent from 2005 to 2015. Rainfall is not similar across the state. Climate change and excessive urbanisation are the causes behind the decline in forest cover. The swamp/Man grows cover has declined from 32.90 per cent to 11.99 per cent from 2005 to 2015 in Nagpur. Snub forest is declining sharply (16.66 per cent to 10.80 per cent) from 2005 to 2015 in Western Maharashtra. The mangrove

coverage remained the same in the Kokan region as compared to other regions in Maharashtra. The island wetlands in the Kokan region have declined from 100 per cent to 11.61 per cent from 2005 to 2015 in Kokan. Many wetlands are filled with mud due to population pressure and an increase in built-up land. The water bodies in Amravati have declined from 30.22 per cent to 12.62 per cent from 2005 to 2015. In the Nagpur region, the land under water bodies has increased from 12.30 per cent to 24.39 per cent from 2005 to 2015. There are more water bodies created in the region.

Table 2. The change of land use in Maharashtra from 2005 to 2015 (Ha)

		Kokan	Western Maharashtra	Nasik	Aurangabad	Amravati	Nagpur	Maharashtra
Agriculture	Crop land	377.46	3871.19	-35789.7	19570.22	9353.78	-25609.6	-28226.7
	Fallow	57.72	-3075.94	-4450.35	1567.22	531.97	-4171.62	-9541
	Plantation	760.48	100.6	-584.259	-260.89	-204.14	-60.9	-249.109
Barren/ unculturable/ Wastelands	Barren Rocky	-1.05	-33.85	-530.511	6.40	-19.78	-289.84	-868.631
	Gullied / Ravinous Land	-2.00	-3.75	-262.40	-175.38	140.64	0.99	-301.902
	Salt Affected Land	-36.22	2.40	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	-33.82
	Sandy Area	-13.8	0.00	-0.63	-3.05	-0.3	-0.32	-18.1
	Scrub Land	-357.52	-822.02	-3467.44	2380.09	81.47	-1977.87	-4163.29
Built-up	Mining	-21.8	-13.27	-28.843	-26.35	-65.01	57.22	-98.0534
	Rural	-133.03	-127.63	-565.37	219.66	-162.12	-136.06	-904.551
	Urban	-225.39	-448.92	-613.42	92.29	-412.64	6.06	-1602.02
Forest	Deciduous	-751.52	702.96	-5355.90	-4743.92	-13928.2	18538.37	-5538.21
	Evergreen/Semi-evergreen	712.78	-74.88	-47.41	0.00	0.35	0.00	590.8407
	Forest Plantation	0.17	3.65	-2.42	-2.02	-223.96	243.03	18.45384
	Scrub Forest	-116.36	-99.77	-3953.98	-869.48	727.37	229.89	-4082.33
	Swamp / Mangroves	-38.68	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	-38.68
Grass / Grazing	Grass / Grazing	0.07	0.15	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.53	1.75
Wetlands / Water bodies	Inland Wetland	912.75	0.00	-1.13	-0.81	-12.52	0.00	898.29
	Coastal Wetland	-1100.24	0.18	-0.79	-0.61	0.00	0.00	-1101.47
	River/Stream/Canals	11.9	-26.78	-801.86	279.41	-586.58	241.75	-882.157
	Water bodies	-35.73	45.68	-936.52	598.17	-565.34	-358.59	-1252.34
		-0.01	0.00	-57393	18630.95	-5345.01	-13286	-57393

Source: Ministry of Environment and Forests, GoI

The changes in land use in Maharashtra from 2005 to 2015 are presented in Table 2. As far as crop land is concerned, in Nasik region it has declined up to 35789.7ha. In the Nagpur region, it has also declined (-25609.6 ha). The farmland has declined (-3075.91 ha) in Nasik (-4450.55 ha) and the Nagpur region (-4171.62 ha). The plantation has declined by 584.25 ha in the Nasik region from 2005 to 2015. It has increased to 760.48 ha in the Kokan region. More land is being brought under plantation in the Kokan region. The Barren rocky land has declined 530.51ha in the Nasik region from 2005 to 2015. The gullied/Ravenous land has declined 262.40 ha in the Nasik region. The salt-affected land has declined 36.22 ha from 2005 to 2015 in the Kokan region. The scrub land has declined 3467.44 ha in the Nasik region. The mining has declined by 65.01 ha in the Amravati region from 2005 to 2015. In the rural area of the Nasik region, the built-up land has declined (-567.37 ha). In the urban area, the built-up area in the Nasik region has declined by -613.42 ha from 2005 to 2015. The deciduous forest cover has declined by 13928.2 ha in the Amravati region. But in the Nagpur region, the deciduous land has increased to 18538.37 ha. Evergreen semi-evergreen forest in the Kokan region increased to 712.78 ha. It is a good achievement as far as the biodiversity of the state is concerned. Forest plantation has declined by -223.96 ha in the Amravati region. As far as the scrub forest is concerned, it had declined (-3953.98 ha) in the Nasik region from 2005 to 2015. The inland wetland has increased in Kokan as 912.75 ha from 2005 to 2015. The land under Rivers/Streams/canals has declined to- 801.85 ha in the Nasik region. The land under water bodies in the Nasik region has declined (-936.52ha) from 2005 to 2015. In the Aurangabad region, water bodies related land has increased (598.17 ha) from 2005 to 2015.

Table 3. The use of land use in Maharashtra from 2005 to 2011(Hector)

		Kokan	Western Maharashtra	Nasik	Aurangabad	Amravati	Nagpur	Maharashtra
Agriculture	Crop land	-177.07	726.99	32965.71	-25499.75	21342.67	8708.24	38066.79
	Current Shifting cultivation	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	Fallow	-268.15	-398.75	3345.44	-4292.83	2521.66	320.82	1228.19
	Plantation	-633.89	-98.20	650.89	-27.09	-168.53	222.62	-54.20
Barren/unculturable/ Wastelands	Barren Rocky	-2.65	44.31	416.63	-32.83	130.29	-5.52	550.23
	Gullied / Ravinous Land	1.29	21.40	273.91	10.98	-159.76	144.00	291.82
	Rann	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	Salt Affected Land	19.53	-2.82	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	16.71
	Sandy Area	0.36	0.00	0.00	-0.15	0.00	0.11	0.32
	Scrub Land	-92.72	-1318.96	2817.83	-2767.92	3080.20	-287.45	1430.98

Built up	Mining	28.62	4.65	27.11	78.82	17.15	-27.43	128.92
	Rural	136.84	109.70	529.46	-78.03	312.53	-86.47	924.03
	Urban	226.60	63.40	369.37	248.11	1017.38	-213.00	1711.86
Forest	Deciduous	996.85	1160.01	3798.11	18790.86	-3192.86	-13720.11	7832.86
	Evergreen/Semi-evergreen	-406.35	-648.61	30.11	0.00	828.09	0.00	-196.76
	Forest Plantation	-0.10	-4.99	3.59	243.26	0.14	-240.98	0.92
	Scrub Forest	-108.79	351.04	2470.66	-6.64	-706.96	584.04	2583.35
	Swamp Mangroves	40.53	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	40.53
Grass / Grazing	Grass / Grazing	-0.07	-0.15	0.00	0.00	0.00	-1.53	-1.75
Wetlands / Water bodies	Inland Wetland	-912.75	1.10	0.03	2.92	0.00	0.81	-907.89
	Coastal Wetland	1130.37	-0.18	0.80	0.00	0.00	0.61	1131.60
	River/Stream/Canals	-10.19	11.46	702.91	285.41	448.60	-542.78	895.41
	Water bodies	31.74	-133.40	945.47	-241.07	1317.46	-201.00	1719.20
		0.00	-112.00	49348.03	-13285.95	26788.06	-5345.02	57393.12

Source: Ministry of Environment and Forests, GoI

The changes in land use in Maharashtra from 2005 to 2011 are presented in Table 3. The crop land has increased in the Nasik region from 32965.71 ha from 2005 to 2011. But it has declined (-25499.75 ha) in the Aurangabad region. The following land has increased by 3345.44 ha in the Nasik region from 2005 to 2011. But it has declined by (-4292.83 ha) in the Aurangabad region from 2005 to 2011. The plantation has declined (-633.89 ha) from 2005 to 2011 in the Kokan region. The plantation has increased to 222.62 ha in the Nagpur region from 2005 to 2011. The Barran Rocky land has increased in the Nasik region from 2005 to 2011 by 416.63 ha. The Gullied/Ravinous land has increased to 273.91 ha from 2005 to 2011 in the Nasik region. It has declined by (-159.76 ha) in the Nasik region from 2005 to 2011. In the Aurangabad region, the scrub land has increased to 3080.20 ha from 2005 to 2011. It has increased as 2817.83 ha in Nasik region from 2005-2011. The built-up area in the rural area of Western Maharashtra has increased to 529.46 ha from 2005 to 2011. In the urban area, the built-up area in the Amravati region has increased to 1017.38 ha from 2005 to 2011. The deciduous land has increased by 18790.86 hectares from 2005 to 2011 in the Aurangabad region. The deciduous land has declined in the Nagpur region (-13720.11 ha) from 2005 to 2011. Evergreen forest land has increased by 828.09 ha in the Amravati region. But in the Western Maharashtra region (-648.61 ha) and the Kokan region (406.3 ha), evergreen forest land has declined from 2005 to 2011. More urbanisation and pressure on land are the reasons for it. The forest plantation has increased to 243.26 ha in the Aurangabad region. But it has declined (-240.98 ha) in the Nagpur region from 2005 to 2011. The scrub forest has increased (2470.66 ha) in the Nasik region and (584.04 ha) in the Nagpur region. But it has declined to

706.96 ha in the Aurangabad region from 2005 to 2011. Inland wetlands have declined by (-912.75 ha) in the Kokan region. The coastal wetlands have increased to 1130.37 ha from 2005 to 2011 in the Kokan region. It is the statistics which shows increase in the wetland area in the region. The land under the river stream/canals has increased in the Nasik region from 2005-2011 to 702.91 ha. In the Nagpur region, it has declined (-542.78 ha) over the period of time. The water bodies have increased to 1317.46 ha in the Amravati and Nasik (945.47 ha) region.

Table 4. The change of land use in Maharashtra from 2011 to 2015 (Hector)

		Kokan	Western Maharashtra	Nasik	Aurangabad	Amravati	Nagpur	Maharashtra
Agriculture	Crop land	-200.39	-4598.18	2824.02	5929.53	-30696.45	16901.37	-9840.10
	Current Shifting cultivation	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	Fallow	210.43	3474.69	1104.91	2725.61	-3053.63	3850.80	8312.81
	Plantation	-126.59	-2.40	-66.63	287.98	372.67	-161.72	303.31
Barren/unculturable / Wastelands	Barren Rocky	3.70	-10.46	113.88	26.43	-110.51	295.36	318.40
	Gullied / Ravinous Land	0.71	-17.65	-11.51	164.40	19.12	-144.99	10.08
	Rann	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	Salt Affected Land	16.69	0.42	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	17.11
	Sandy Area	13.44	0.00	0.63	3.20	0.30	0.21	17.78
	Scrub Land	450.24	2140.98	649.61	387.83	-3161.67	2265.32	2732.31
Builtup	Mining	-6.82	8.62	1.73	-52.47	47.86	-29.79	-30.87
	Rural	-3.81	17.93	35.91	-141.63	-150.41	222.53	-19.48
	Urban	-1.21	385.52	244.05	-340.40	-604.74	206.94	-109.84
Forest	Deciduous	-245.33	-1862.97	1557.79	-14046.94	17121.06	-4818.26	-2294.65
	Evergreen/Semi-evergreen	-306.43	723.49	17.30	0.00	-828.44	0.00	-394.08
	Forest Plantation	-0.07	1.34	-1.17	-241.24	223.82	-2.05	-19.37
	Scrub Forest	225.15	-251.27	1483.32	876.12	-20.41	-813.93	1498.98
	Swamp / Mangroves	-1.85	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	-1.85
Wetlands / Water bodies	Inland Wetland	0.00	-1.10	1.10	-2.11	12.52	-0.81	9.60
	Coastal Wetland	-30.13	0.00	0.00	0.61	0.00	-0.61	-30.13
	River/Stream/Canals	-1.71	15.32	98.95	-564.82	137.98	301.03	-13.25
	Water bodies	3.99	87.72	-8.94	-357.10	-752.12	559.59	-466.86
		0.01	112.00	8044.95	-5345.00	-21443.05	18630.99	-0.10

Source: Ministry of Environment and Forests, GoI

The changes in land use in Maharashtra from 2011 to 2015 are presented in Table 4. The crop land has declined (-30696.45 ha) in the Amravati region and (-4598.18 ha) in the Western Maharashtra region. It has increased in the Nagpur region to 16901.37 ha. More land is brought

under crop land in this region. The fellow land has increased by 3474.69 ha in Western Maharashtra from 2011 to 2015. The plantation has increased in the Amravati region (372.67 ha) and the Aurangabad region (287.98 ha) from 2011 to 2015. The land under commercial crops has grown more in this area. The Barren Rocky land has grown in the Nasik region (113.88 ha) and the Nagpur region (295.36 ha). The gullied/Ravenous land has increased in the Aurangabad region (164.40 ha), but it declined (-144.99 ha) in the Nagpur region from 2011 to 2015. The scrub land has increased to 2140.98 ha in Western Maharashtra and Nagpur (2265.32 ha) region from 2011-15. It has declined by (-3161.67 ha) from 2011-15 in the Aurangabad region. The mining has declined very slightly (-52.47 ha) hector in the Aurangabad region from 2011to 2015. The government does not give permission for mining due to environmentalists and other activists. The built-up area has increased to 222.53 ha in the Nagpur region. The Nagpur region is a fast-developing state. But built-up land has declined in the Amravati (-150.41 ha) region from 2011 to 2015. In the urban area, the built-up area has increased by 385.52 ha in the Western Maharashtra region. Urbanisation is very high, and people from other states are settling in Pune, Satara, and Sangli districts. It has declined to -604.74ha in the Amravati region from 2011 to 2015. The deciduous forest has declined in the Aurangabad region (-14046.94 ha) and the Western Maharashtra region (-1862.97 ha) from 2011-15. But it has increased to (17121.06 ha) in the Amravati region over the period of study. The evergreen /semi-green forest has decreased (828.44 ha) in Amravati, but it has increased in Western Maharashtra (723.49 ha). The forest plantation has declined (-241.24 ha) in the Aurangabad region.

Difference 2015 vs 2005

As far as crop land is concerned, in the Nasik region (35789.7ha) and the Nagpur (-25609.6 ha) region, it has declined over the period. The farmland has declined in the Nasik region (-3075.91 ha), Nasik (-4450.55 ha), and the Nasik region (-4171.62 ha). The plantation has declined by 584.25 ha in the Nasik region from 2005 to 2015. It has increased to 760.48 ha in the Kokan region. The Barren rocky has declined 530.51ha in the Nasik region from 2005 to 2015. The gullied/Ravenous land has declined 262.40 ha in the Nasik region. The salt-affected land has declined 36.22 ha from 2005 to 2015 in the Kokan region. The scrub land has declined 3467.44 ha in the Nasik region. The mining has declined by around 65.01 ha in the Amravati region from 2005 to 2015. In the rural area of the Nasik region, the built-up land has declined (-567.37 ha). In the urban area, the built-up area in the Nasik region has declined by -613.42 ha from 2005 to 2015. The deciduous forest cover has declined by 13928.2 ha in the Amravati

region. But in the Nagpur region, the deciduous land has increased to 18538.37 ha. Evergreen semi-evergreen forest in the Kokan region increased to 712.78 ha. Forest plantation has declined by -223.96 ha in the Amravati region. As far as the scrub forest is concerned, in the Nasik region, it had declined (-3953.98 ha) from 2005 to 2015. The inland wetland has increased in the Kokan region as 912.75 ha from 2005 to 2015. It is a very small increase in wetlands in the Kokan region. In parts of Thane, Raigad, and Mumbai district, inland wetlands are declining fast. Rivers/Streams/canals have declined by 801.85 ha in the Nasik region. The water bodies in the Nasik region have declined (-936.52ha) from 2005 to 2015. In the Aurangabad region, water bodies related land has increased (598.17 ha) from 2005 to 2015. It has increased in the Amravati (223.82 ha) region from 2011 to 2015. The scrub forest has increased by 1483.32 ha in the Nasik region, but it has declined in the Nagpur (-813.93 ha) region from 2011 to 2015. The coastal wetland has declined (-30.13 ha) in the Kokan region from 2011 to 2015. It is a very small hectare of land in the region. The river/stream/canal's related land has declined (-564.82 ha) in Aurangabad, but it has increased in the Nagpur region (301.03 ha) during 2011-15. The land under water bodies has increased in Aurangabad (559.95 ha). Due to water scarcity in the region, the land was brought under water bodies. But it has declined in the Nagpur (-752.12 ha) region. From the above statistics, we can see that there are several human activities that harm these natural ecosystems. If we don't value the importance of natural resources, wetlands will be further degraded. Evolution in any field gives more facilities and opportunities for humans. In the past, some decades, people were ignorant about protecting the earth's environment, which resulted in the loss of the natural ecosystem. Wetland degradation and loss are major issues in the current situation. Not only small water bodies but largest wetlands are fragmented or degraded due to human activities. Wetland degradation prevents several issues like pollution, climate change, loss of natural habitat, etc., and these problems directly affect the environment (Kuchara et al., 2023).

Table 5. Geographic area, wetland area in Maharashtra

District	Geographic Area (sq.km)	Wetland Area (Ha)	Total wetland area (Per cent)	District geographic area (Per cent)
Konkan Division:	30728	155783	15.37	53.99
Pune Division:	57270	178777	17.62	14.9
Nashik Division:	57502	185522	18.28	15.78
Aurangabad Division:	64809	201616	19.87	24.93
Nagpur Division:	51377	194621	19.19	24.6
Amravati Division:	46062	98203	9.68	10.72

Source: Ministry of Environment and Forests, GoI

The above table shows that the geographic area of the Kokan division is 30728sq.km and the wetland area is 155783 ha. It is 15.37 per cent of the total wetland area (Table 5). In the Kokan region, the percentage of the district's geographic area is 54 percent. It is the highest district area in the state of Maharashtra. The Aurangabad region has a geographic area of 64809 sq. km. The wetland area is 201616 ha (19.87 per cent). It is highest wetland cover in terms of percent in the state. The percent of the district's geographic area is 24.93 percent. In the Amravati region, the geographic area is 46062sq.km. The wetland area is 98203 ha. The percent of total wetland area is 9.68 percent, but the geographic area as a percent of the district is only 10.72 percent. The Amravati division has a low percentage of area and district geographic area under wetlands. We can further see the area under the wetland in different regions of the state.

Table 6. Wetland area in the region of Maharashtra (Number)

Wet code	Level I Level II Level III	Kokan	Nasik	Western Maharashtra	Amravati	Nagpur	Aurangabad	Maharashtra
1100	Inland Wetlands – Natural							
1101	Lakes/Ponds	7	0	28	1	1	2	39
1102	Ox-bow lakes/ Cut-off meanders	0	0	1	0	0	1	2
1104	Riverine wetlands	0	0	1	0	0	0	1
1105	Waterlogged	4	22	1	0	0	9	35
1106	River/Stream	322	1625	533	470	1930	721	3501
1200	Inland Wetlands – Man-made							
1201	Reservoirs/Barrages	15	178	193	57	53	337	759
1202	Tanks/Ponds	518	3407	1764	1591	5243	4093	1580
1203	Waterlogged	0	10	20	0	0	7	37
	Total – Inland							
2100	Coastal Wetlands – Natural							
2102	Creeks	162	0	0	0	0	0	162
2103	Sand/Beach	390	0	0	0	0	0	390
2104	Intertidal mud flats	740	0	0	0	0	0	740
2105	Salt Marshes	29	0	0	0	0	0	29
2106	Mangroves	1251	0	0	0	0	0	1251
2200	Coastal Wetlands – Man-made							
2201	Salt pans	205	0	0	0	0	0	205
2202	Aquaculture ponds	4	2	0	0	0	0	6
	Wetlands (<2.25 ha), mainly Tanks	1437	5242	2587	940	8895	1528	20635

Source: Ministry of Environment and Forests, GoI

Wetland areas in different regions of Maharashtra are presented in Table 6. The lakes in western Maharashtra are the highest (28) as far as other regions are concerned. Major dams are built in Western Maharashtra for irrigation and water supply. A few dams are in the Kolhapur, Satara, and Pune districts. The waterlogged areas are 22 in the Nasik region. The rivers/streams are 470 in the Amravati region. The Aurangabad region has 721 river streams. The Amravati has 57 ha of reservoirs. The Amravati region has 1591 tanks /bonds. The water level at Aurangabad was 9. The Kokan region of Maharashtra has very high biodiversity with natural resources. There are 162 creeks in Kokan. Many tourists visit such places in the summer. The salt marshes are 29, and man grows sites are 1251 in Kokan. A total of 205 salt pans were observed in Kokan. It is clearly related to seawater, and due to the Arabian Sea location, salt pans are in the Kokan region. The aquaculture ponds were 4 in Kokan, and in Western Maharashtra, they are only 2 in number.

Table 7. The wetland area in different regions of Maharashtra (Hectors)

Code	Wetland area	Kokan	Nasik	Western Maharashtra	Amravati	Nagpur	Aurangabad	Maharashtra
1100	Inland Wetlands – Natural							
1101	Lakes/Ponds	2699	0	4371	116	1805	5	8880.68
1102	Ox-bow lakes/ Cut-off meanders	0	0	12	0	0	0	0
1104	Riverine wetlands	0	0	2	0	0	0	2
1105	Waterlogged	17	155	3	0	0	115	290
1106	River/Stream	26966	77089	43052	34366	103894	46125	297308.6
1200	Inland Wetlands - Man-made							
1201	Reservoirs/Barrages	3270	85721	86892	32033	45807	89792	311633.6
1202	Tanks/Ponds	6785	37445	17920	30742	71865	42683	176857.5
1203	Waterlogged	0	56	77	0	0	169	302
	Total – Inland							
2100	Coastal Wetlands – Natural							
2102	Creeks	41636	0	0	0	0	0	41636
2103	Sand/Beach	4794	0	0	0	0	0	4794
2104	Intertidal mud flats	22241	0	0	0	0	0	22241
2105	Salt Marshes	584	0	0	0	0	0	584
2106	Mangroves	29981	0	0	0	0	0	29981
2200	Coastal Wetlands - Man-made							

2201	Salt pans	7025	0	0	0	0	0	7025
2202	Aquaculture ponds	46	25	0	0	0	0	71
	Wetlands (<2.25 ha), mainly Tanks	1437	5242	2587	946	8895	1528	19694.62

Source: Ministry of Environment and Forests, GoI

Wetland areas in different regions of Maharashtra are presented in Table 7. There are 2699 ponds observed in the Kokan region. Due to proximity to the Arabian Sea, there are many ponds in the Kokan region. During high tides, water enters many villages along a 720 km coastline. In Western Maharashtra, there are 4371 ha of ponds/lakes. Many lakes are made to tackle water scarcity in the region. The waterlogged were 115 ha in the Nasik region. The river/stream could be 103894 ha in the Nagpur region. The reservoirs /Barrages could be 89792 ha in the Aurangabad region. Tanks and pond area could be 71865 ha in the Nagpur region. To tackle water scarcity, many ponds have been built over the period. In the Aurangabad region, the tanks/ponds area could be 42683 ha. Waterlogged could be 169ha in the Aurangabad division. The creeks were 41636 ha in the Kokan region. The sand beach was 4794 ha in the Kokan region. Tourists visit such beaches regularly in the Kokan region. The tidal mud flats were 22241 ha in the Kokan region. The area under salt marches was 584 ha in the Kokan region. The area under salt marches was 584 ha in the Kokan region. The area under mangroves in the Kokan region is 29981 ha. Man grows are natural habitats to many birds and species. The aquaculture pond had an area of 46 ha in the Kokan region. In western Maharashtra, it is 25 ha. Wetland ecosystems provide multiple benefits to human settlements; nonetheless, they are threatened by human activities associated mainly with urban growth. There is a need for continuous monitoring by regulatory authorities to ensure compliance with extant laws on wetland ecosystem management. Human activities (both individuals and government) that degrade wetlands should be reduced, while efforts should be made on those activities that encourage wetland conservation and preservation (Yager et al., 2024)

Ordinary least squares regression results

We have used the ordinary least squares regression (Greene, 2003) to understand the factors associated with total land use in Maharashtra.

$$Y_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \dots + \epsilon \quad (11)$$

Were,

Y_i is the dependent variable as total land use in the state for different purposes

X1 to Xn are independent variables as regions, and the use of land for different purposes.

€ is the error term in the above equation

Land is available for different purposes, and there is a drastic change in the land use pattern in Maharashtra. We have used such a regression for different regions and periods. The results are presented as follows.

Table 8. The region-wise regression results

Variable	2015		2011		2005	
	Coefficient	T test	Coefficient	T test	Coefficient	T test
Kokan	1.07 (0.10)	9.96	.89*(0.07)	13.21	1.00* (0.00)	2398230.90
Western Maha	1.09(0.11)	9.43	1.65*(0.16)	9.75	0.99*(0.00)	1166.18
Amravati	2.64(0.35)	7.51	-	-	1.00*(0.00)	861048.52
Nagpur	0.729* (0.10)	7.09	1.22*(0.03)	48.77	1.00*(0.00)	394080.98
Aurangabad	0.775* (0.19)	3.99	1.16*(0.16)	7.00	1.00*(0.00)	2087338.52
constant	89.907** (119.90)	0.75	-87.10 (82.12)	-1.06	6.73(0.00)	0.128
R	R Square=1.00 Adjusted R Square=1.00	Std. Error of the Estimate	R =1, R Square=1 Adjusted R Square=1.00	Std. Error of the Estimate	R =1, R Square=1	Std. Error of the Estimate
1.000 ^a	1.000	475.53	1.000	323.74	Adjusted R Square=1.00	.002

*Significant at 1 percent ** significant at 5 percent

The regression results presented in Table 8 indicate that we have classified the wetland resources in Maharashtra. We found that in 2015, the wetlands were significant in Kokan, western Maharashtra, Amravati, Nagpur, and Aurangabad region. Such regions have high wetlands, and they are important for that region. In 2011, the wetlands were statistically significant in Kokan, Nasik, and Western Maharashtra. Nagpur and the Aurangabad region. For 2005, the wetlands are significant in Kokan Nasik, Western Maharashtra, Amravati, Nagpur, and Aurangabad region. From all the regions, Kokan and Western Maharashtra, Nagpur, and Aurangabad regions are statistically significant and positively correlated to the total land under different uses in the state.

Table 9. The Ordinary least squares regression results as per land use and years

Variables	Subcategory	2005		2011		2015	
		Coefficient	T test	Coefficient	T test	Coefficient	T test
Agriculture	Crop land			2.428*** (0.82)	2.967	0.89*(0.12)	7.03
Barren/unculturable/ Wastelands	Barren Rocky	-20.316** (0.11)	- 182.549				
	Gullied / Ravinous Land	117.16** (0.21)	556.26				
Built up	Mining						
	Urban					13.05*** (4.98)	2.62
	Evergreen/Semi evergreen			34.23** (6.12)	5.59		

	Forest Plantation	14.32** (0.15)	91.48				
Wetlands / Water bodies	Inland Wetland	25.04** (0.04)	677.17				
	River/Stream/Canals			1.12**(0.22)	5.09	24.16*** (8.00)	3.02
	Water bodies	50.04* (0.02)	1949.97	-8.95(8.26)	-1.08		
	Constant	-2.63 (16.20)	-0.16	54.69(1693.10)		259.71*** (2187.99)	0.12
		R=1.00, R ² =1.00 Adjusted R ²	Std. Error of the Estimate	R ² =1.00, Adjusted R ² =0.99	Std. Error of the Estimate	R =1.00, R ² =0.99, Adjusted R ² =0.99	Std. Error of the Estimate
		1.000	31.01919	R=1	3200.70623		4146.42816

*Significant at 1 percent ** significant at 5 percent

The ordinary least squares regression results presented in Table 9 indicate that in 2005, the barren Ricky land was negatively correlated with the total land of Maharashtra in 2005. The gullied Ravenous land is statistically significant. The forest plantation was statistically significant in 2005. The island wetlands were significant in the 2005 survey. The water bodies were statistically significant in 2005 in terms of total land. The area under water bodies is higher and statistically significant. Over the period, due to irregular rainfall, the water scarcity has increased. The state has built many ponds for farmers. During 2011, the crop land area was statistically significant compared to the total inland. The evergreen/semi-evergreen land is positive and statistically significant. The water bodies are negatively correlated to the total land in the state. Such a relationship is statistically significant. The land under water bodies is not covered for the whole year. Farmers developed irrigation facilities. They use maximum water for commercial crops. In 2015, the total land use in urban areas was statistically significant and positively correlated to urban areas. The crop land is statistically significant and positively correlated with total land. The river/stream/canals were statistically significant and positively correlated with total land. The rivers in the state have covered the maximum area.

Table 10. The ordinary least squares regression: A comparison of 2005,2011 and 2015

Variable	Co-efficient	Standard error	T test
Crop land	1.11	0.05	24.96
Salt Affected Land	-165.40	71.18	-2.32
Scrub Land	3.12	0.37	8.49
Deciduous	1.14	0.06	18.53
Inland Wetland	-1471.07**	653.29	-2.25
Coastal Wetland	1055.59***	578.42	1.82
Water bodies	5.88**	1.83	3.21
2005	6.27**	1.53	4.10
2015	-3.54**	1.85	-1.91
Constant	1754.63	1022.03	1.71
R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	Std. Error of the Estimate
0.999 ^a	0.999	0.997	942.57102

*Significant at 1 percent ** significant at 5 percent *** significant at 10 percent

The ordinary least squares regression results presented in Table 10 indicate that the crop land is positively correlated and statistically significant with total land. The salt-affected land is negatively correlated and statistically significant with total land. There is a strong law against the conversion of salt-affected land to build an area. The scrub land is statistically significant and positively correlated with total land. The deciduous land is statistically significant and positively correlated with total land. Every year, vegetation grows on this land. The inland water is negatively correlated and statistically significant with total land. The coastal wetlands are statistically significant and positively correlated with total land. Coastal wetlands play a significant role in creation, biodiversity, and protection from natural disasters. The water bodies are statistically significant and positively correlated with total land use. Now, maximum water bodies are created to store water. The state government has invested in the creation of storage facilities. The year 2005 is statistically significant and positively correlated with total land use in Maharashtra. This year, there is not much difference in the land use for different categories in the state. In 2015, the land use was negatively correlated with total land use in Maharashtra. We can say that in 2015, the land under different categories has declined, and it is statistically significant.

Policy implication

Wetlands are the kidneys of the earth, and they provide a number of services to people. The loss of natural wetland area directly affects human development, flora and fauna, animals, birds, fish, and others in water bodies. The degradation of wetland clearly effects on habitat quality and the habitat degradation. Human activities appeared as the most important driver of habitat quality, but unfortunately, due to a lack of knowledge and understanding, the quality of habitats is deteriorating. Rising urbanization and population growth are the major factors responsible for wetland degradation in Maharashtra. Due to population growth, land is converted into other land. The land is converted, and houses are built for people. Builder lobby is behind the land conversion and the built-up area growth. People of the region are also responsible for the degradation of wetlands. They understand very little about the habitats, birds, their reproduction process, and their interdependence on nature. A few industrialists also degrade the wetlands through encroachment on land for production purposes and the release of industrial sewage into the wetlands. The government provides fertile land under concession to industrialists. While building their production plants and roads, they destroy the wetlands and natural biodiversity. People are encroaching on wetlands in urban areas for building houses.

The State government of Maharashtra must come out with a clear policy paper for the development and conservation of wetlands. The immediate policy required is to maintain wetlands and habitat quality. Wetlands are important for ecological conservation and sustainable development (Xing et al., 2023). Wetlands are declining in the Kokan region due to excessive pressure from urbanisation and infrastructure projects. The state government is responsible for the loss of wetlands in Mumbai, Thane, and Raigad districts. The crop land is declining in western Maharashtra. More land is converted into a residential area. Pune, Satara, and Sangali are examples of excessive urbanisation. The state government must have a clear policy related to the protection and sustainability of mangroves in the Kokan region. In Western Maharashtra and the Kokan region, due to excessive migration, inland wetlands are filled with rocks and mud, and land is made available for residential purposes. The builder lobby took maximum advantage of the state government policies related to housing. The trend of migration is more from rural to urban areas, and it will be continuous in the future too. But it does not mean that all the urban wetlands will be filled with debris, and houses will be constructed. There is a need to reserve areas for wetlands in every region. If any wetland is used for government projects, then alternative sites must be conserved as wetlands. The state government must have a uniform policy across departments to protect wetlands in the state. People in rural areas must come forward to protect the biodiversity in villages. There is a need of experts group of environmentalists, economists, agriculturalists, engineers, and researchers to keep pressure on the state government for wetland conservation and protection. With local needs, resource planning is most important, and experts need to be appointed on an immediate basis at the district and tahsil level. All the above policies will certainly help to protect and conserve the wetlands in Maharashtra state. Maharashtra state will come out with the best conservation plan for wetlands protection and conservation if all the above policies are followed on time.

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